

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: MARAFI

FIRST NAME: HAMZA

PROGRAM CODE: DSDD

COURSE CODE: ACA 401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics
 The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:
 The author uses Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)
 The author uses Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)
 My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%
 The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA 401D

1. One of the following is not among the five general aims of research projects;
 - Ask a question worth answering
 - Find an answer that you can support with good reasons
 - Find good data that you can use as reliable evidence to support your reasons
 - Find an answer to the world's problem¹**

2. In academic research, a problem is defined as;
 - Something we try to avoid
 - Something we seek out or even invent²**
 - A mistake worth exploring
 - Something imposes on us by nature

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¹ [Kate L. Turabian](#), *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations; Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth Ed. (Chicago: University Press, 2018) 23.

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² Ibid., 29.

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3. One of the following statements is an incorrect reason for citing your sources in academic research;

- To give credit to the authors
- To help readers expand their library³**
- To reassure readers about the accuracy of your facts
- To show readers the research tradition that informs your work

4. According to the EU style of reference;

- All footnotes end with a semicolon, except those consisting solely of internet or email address
- All footnotes end with a full stop, except those consisting solely of the internet or email address⁴**
- All footnotes end with a comma, except those consisting solely of internet or email address
- All footnotes end with a colon, except those consisting solely of the internet or email address

5. One of the following is incorrect about citation management tools;

- It enables researchers to keep track of data source
- It enables researchers to double-check data sources
- It enables researchers to compile a list of sources consulted
- It enables researchers to double-check the spelling⁵**

³ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers*, 23.

⁴ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook of Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth Ed. (Brussels: European Commission, 2021) 7.

⁵ Linda D. Bloomberg and Volpe F. Marie, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Fourth Ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 77-202.

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6. All but one of the following are attributes of the review of literature;
- Reviews primary sources that are most recent empirical studies from scholarly journals and publications, as well as secondary sources
 - States up front the bodies of literature that will be covered and why
 - Synthesizes findings across studies and compares and contrasts different research outcomes, perspectives, or methods
 - Write your research finding with notes and recommendations⁶**
7. One of the following is not a definition of Qualitative research;
- It is a field that crosscuts disciplines and subject matters
 - It includes traditions associated with foundationalism, positivism and post-positivism
 - It is connected to cultural and interpretive studies through many perspectives and methods
 - It derives research inferences from the quantitative world⁷**
8. Case study methodology could be categorized into all but one of the following;
- exploratory
 - Descriptive
 - Instrumental
 - Reactive⁸**
9. A research proposal is a well-thought-out written action plan that identifies;
- a broad and ambiguous problem statement;

⁶ [Linda D. Bloomberg and Volpe F. Marie, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 78.](#)

⁷ [Ibid.](#), 143.

⁸ [Ibid.](#), 145.

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- a purpose statement that describes how the problem will be addressed⁹
- Research questions that are not tied to the purpose and, when answered
- Review of the literature and relevant research to determine the research impact

10. Plagiarism could be defined as a situation where a researcher;

- Uses and cite all source of information consulted
- Take someone else words or ideas and give them credit
- Take someone else ideas and words without giving credit to the authors¹⁰
- Consulted different sources and listed them in the reference

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⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/401D Course pack: Period 1*. Fourth Ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 159.

¹⁰ Ibid., 202.

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